

IPBES TCA Chapter 1. DMR 1.2. Analysis of contributions on what transformative change is according to different communities of knowledge / IPBES transformative change assessment

Code: IPBES_TCA_1.2_knowledgeCommunities

Versioning 01: 30.11.2023

Versioning 02: 25.06.2024

Versioning 03: 16.10.2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10246572>

Project leaders:

Julia Leventon (leventon.j@czechglobe.cz)

Researchers:

Juan Martin Dabezies (jmdabezies@cure.edu.uy)

Janita Gurung (janita.gurung@icimod.org)

Adla Kahric (adla.k@hotmail.com)

Josheena Naggea (josheena.naggea@gmail.com)

Teresia Olemako (trolemak@yahoo.com)

Jerneja Penca (jerneja.penca@zrs-kp.si)

Asha Rajvanshi (asharajvanshi@gmail.com)

Roseline Remans (r.remans@cgiar.org)

Esther Turnhout (e.turnhout@utwente.nl)

Fern Wickson (fern.wickson@uit.no)

Yuki Yoshida (y.yoshida.tokyo@gmail.com)

Data curator:

Anouk Renaud (anouk.renaud@umontpellier.fr)

Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 1 should explain what transformative change is. The chapter documents the various demands for, and conceptualizations and understandings of transformative change. In this context, a review of contributions provided by different communities of knowledge was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Protocol

Starting point

Identifying the three dimensions and four principles for transformative change draws on an expert-led review process. This is a form of semi-systematic review. An expert-led review starts with experts as the entry point into selecting literature for inclusion in the review. This review is therefore a critical form of review that identifies a selection of evidence that represents a broader body of work.

Identification of knowledge communities

This expert-led approach has taken place in two stages. Firstly, the assessment experts for Chapter 1 (Coordinating Lead Authors and Lead Authors) used their diverse viewpoints to identify 7 knowledge communities that explore topics of transformative change and would have evidence to contribute on what transformative change is and how it occurs. These communities include 4 communities that are predominantly academic research perspectives. The further 3 are sources of non-academic knowledge that are at risk of under-representation in academic work. The authors recognise that these are not mutually exclusive communities with hard borders; they overlap and any one person might consider themselves in multiple communities. However, by ensuring that there is evidence from all communities, the diversity of understandings that is incorporated into this assessment is increased.

- Systems
- Relational
- Individual
- Structural
- Indigenous knowledge
- Spiritual and religion
- Youth and social movements

Searching and inviting potential contributing authors

For all communities, the chapter team identified a set of experts (A). These experts were identified based on their publications, project work and practice activities, as people who could give a solid overview of their approaches and theoretical positions within the community of knowledge. They needed to have a good critical knowledge of the broader topics with the community and be able to cover topics including and beyond biodiversity. For those topics that are predominantly non-academic knowledge, the authors selected people who had enough engagement with academic practices that they would be able to provide references and published evidence; such references would not necessarily include academic papers, but include accurate citations to grey literature and policy documentation.

These experts have been invited to be contributing authors and were asked to provide text (around 1000 words) with references (ideally 20 to 30) on how their community addresses the topic of transformative change (B). No contributing author was excluded if they chose to include fewer references, and their text was counted with the same weight as any other contributor.

The assessment authors took particular care to invite contributions from Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Some of the potential contributing authors from the Indigenous and local knowledge community, were identified and approached via the IPBES Indigenous and local knowledge technical support unit. This proved challenging, with numerous requests unanswered or declined due to the high workloads of the approached contributing authors. As a consequence, 16 contributing authors were approached on the topic of Indigenous and local knowledge, and 5 contributions were received (see table 1 and file (A)).

Analysis of the contributions

The references provided were then studied by the chapter team (C). For each community of knowledge, references directly relevant to the scope of the chapter, and understanding what makes change transformative, were selected. This selection was based on title, abstract and the way it was used within the contributing author’s text. Due to the differing numbers of contributing authors, the different numbers of references they provided (and scope for overlap therein), and the different amounts of evidence available within these communities, the numbers of papers/documents reviewed varies by community (see table 1).

Contributions and the selected references were reviewed iteratively by the chapter authors. Initially, contributions were explored for how they referred to the dimensions of views, structures and practices (see Chapter 1 section 1.3.1), with the emerging definitions of each, and concepts included therein, developing to account for findings. Similar inductive coding was done for the four principles (see Chapter 1 section 1.3.2) allowing their meanings across different knowledge communities to emerge.

When discussing practices, many of the contributions and recommended references discussed, studied or proposed actions for creating change. These were synthesised into the categories of roles that people can play in the process of transformative change (see Chapter 1 section 1.4.2, table 1.1).

Community	CAs approached	Contributions from Cas received	Documents reviewed
Systems	5	5	31
Relational	12	7	65
Individual	17	5	27
Structures	7	3	49

Indigenous knowledge	16	4 ¹	48
Spiritual and Religion	3	2	25
Youth	2	2	9

Table 1: Contributions per community of knowledge

Contributions received and subsequent numbers of documents reviewed. There is significant blurring of the boundaries between different knowledge communities, and therefore higher numbers in one community do not necessarily mean a greater incorporation of that particular viewpoint in the review. For example, some papers collected under ‘relational’ could alternatively be categorised as ‘systems’.

Indigenous knowledge community

The documents reviewed for the Indigenous knowledge community are in the file [\(C\)](#).

For the Indigenous and local knowledge community, the authors took an additional approach that worked with evidence being collected from the existing dialogues processes in IPBES, and the call for evidence released on 31 May 2023.

- This call for evidence resulted in a Zotero database of Indigenous and local knowledge. The database contains 118 resources.
 - These were imported into NVIVO 12 and images, videos, web pages, references with errors and texts that are not in English or Spanish were excluded. Only 72 texts in English and Spanish remained.
 - Materials in other languages were excluded due to lack of language capacity to assess them within the assessment team.
 - The categories of power, practice, structures and worldviews (and its translations in Spanish), were used to analyse the resources.
 - From this first round of analysis, the 29 resources that had a least 10 or more references to each category (power, practices, structures, views) were selected for in-depth analysis. These were scrutinised to find the content in relation to transformative change and the different Chapter 1 sections and contents and to understand how they were framing views, structures and practices.
 - Quantitative analyses (Table 2) show a strong presence of content linked to practice. Then the category power also had a strong presence, followed by structure and worldview.
 - Initially, the category of “power” was also used to analyse resources, however assessment authors did not include these references as such in the Chapter 1 final draft.

¹ Not all documents reviewed for Indigenous knowledge were suggested by contributing authors. Rather, an additional process was followed for this community, as described below.

Name	Resources	References
Power	52	391
Practice	56	757
Structure	49	188
Worldview	31	107

Table 2. Coding frequency of categories used (power, practice, worldview and structure).

Resources refers to the text indexed in Zotero (Indigenous and local knowledge Call for Contributions Database relative to transformative change) and reference to the category mentioned in that resource. For example, the category “practice” is mentioned by 56 texts in a total of 757 times considering all the 56 texts.

Definition of files

ID	Names	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR1.2_knowledgeCommunities_(A)	pdf	154 KB	List of invited potential and confirmed contributing authors
B	2_IPBES_TCA_DMR1.2_knowledgeCommunities_(B)	pdf	130 KB	Invitation letter and instructions sent to the contributing authors
C	3_IPBES_TCA_DMR1.2_knowledgeCommunities_(C)	csv	125 KB	References received from the contributing authors
D	4_IPBES_TCA_DMR1.2_knowledgeCommunities_(D)	csv	9 KB	References for the Indigenous knowledge community